

Influence of Competition Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance in Secondary Schools in Nakuru County, Kenya

Lydia Wambui Mwangi Waiya^{a*}

^{a*} Department of Psychology, Counseling and Educational Foundations Laikipia University, P.O. Box 1100 – 20300. Nyahururu, Kenya.

Submitted: 10-10-2019

Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to analyze influence of Competition Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance in Secondary Schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design targeting 3,584 form two and three students in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. A sample of 351 students was drawn using purposive and stratified random sampling. Data was collected through structured self-administered questionnaires. Hypothesis was tested using regression analysis of .05 level of significance. Data was analyzed by the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer package Version 22.0. The findings of this study may enable coaches to come up with appropriate mechanisms that may help athletes manage their stress effectively. Similarly it may help secondary schools in Kenya institute appropriate interventions to help athletes cope with the stress associated with their sporting careers. The study will also help in building on existing literature related to sources of stress, coping strategies and school based interventions among students athlete in secondary schools. The study will also suggest areas of further research that will create ground for researchers interested in the topic, thus contributing to the expansion of knowledge in the field of counseling psychology. The study established that competition related stress negatively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study recommends that the Ministry of Education in Conjunction with Department of Sports of the Ministry of Social Services should develop Secondary School Sports Policy with Sports Stress Management Guidelines to help manage the emerging sports related stress in Secondary Schools in Kenya. Copies of the policy should be availed in all Secondary Schools in Kenya for use by both Games Masters and Teacher Counsellors ion the Schools.

Key Words: *Athletics related stress, Stress Management, Competition Related Stress, Athletics Track Performance.*

* Corresponding author Tel: (+254 722 503 484). E-mail: waiyalw@gmail.com

1.0 Introduction

The competitive sport arena is a highly demanding and potentially stressful environment. In line with this perspective of stress, Fletcher, Hanton and Mellalieu (2006) acknowledge that sport performers must manage a wide range of environmental demands and psychological responses if they are to enhance their athletic performance and sport experience. According to Mellalieu and Hanton (2008) although some performers are able to manage the various causes and consequences of the stress process, many others struggle, resulting in severe impairments to their performance.

Sources of stress in sports have been identified and several of them appear to be common in most sports, suggesting that there could be a core group of stressors experienced by all athletes. These common stressors are; pressure to perform at a high standard, concerns about training, institution and competition environment, individual's personality, coaches' behaviors and coaching styles, and difficulties balancing sport and non-sport commitments (Lombardo, Tan, Jensen and Anderson, 2005).

In Kenya, Sports are important in educational institutions as it supports academic performance. However, it has been viewed in two different perspectives in schools as far as their contribution to school connectedness is concerned. One perceives sports as having positive effect on student academic performance while others view it as a hindrance to academic success and a waste of students' precious time. Therefore, this duality in the perception of the contribution of sports should be corrected through research findings. Besides, it is important to note that sports can assume other functions other than the traditional function of entertainment and leisure. These functions include; supporting academic objectives, boosting students' self-concept, self-efficacy, affective needs, behavioural needs, social needs, discipline, retention rates among others (Ongonga *et al.*, 2010). Sports are now part of academic curriculum in schools under co-curriculum activities by Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD, 2000).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Kenya is known for its athletic prowess, however, its performance is getting threatened and athletes seem to be resorting to unconventional ways of dealing with their stress related problems. Since athletic talent is mainly identified and discovered in secondary school students, this study set out to examine and provide information on student track athletes' stress level and how it influences performance. Athletes in public secondary schools experience stress like other elite athletes. The stress is contributed by different factors which if not addressed may affect their track performance. It is not clear whether competition related stress influences students' athletes on track performance of public secondary school student athletes especially in Nakuru County. This is the research gap that this study was to fill. The hypothesis of the study was stated as Ho₁: There is no statistically significant influence of competition related stress on student track athletes' performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Completion Related Stress and Students Athletics Performance

Competition is prevalent across society. Competitive stressors are defined as the environmental demands associated primarily and directly with competitive performance (Hanton, Mellalieu & Fletcher, 2006). Collectively findings of these studies, stressors experienced in relation to competitive performance include preparation, injuries, pressure, underperforming, expectations, self-presentation, and rivalry (Hanton, Mellalieu & Fletcher, 2006). For example, a businessman "achieves" a promotion, the prime minister "wins" the general election, a pupil is "top of the class" and a boxer "defeats" his opponent (Cooke, 2010).

Moreover, the social comparison and evaluation associated with competition, often includes rewards for success. For instance, in the Olympic Games, the fastest athlete is awarded the most prestigious gold medal, while the third fastest runner receives the impressive, but less important bronze (Jayantha & Ubayachandra, 2015).

Mapfuno and Muchene (2014) established that the first sources of stress found among the ZNYG Manicaland chapter athletes are the same found among athletes around the world. Sources include injury and illness, pressure of completion, the coach, referee and the spectators. Stress on the ZNYG athletes need to be controlled or eradicated lest it hinders sports excellence. On coping styles it can be concluded that most of the ZNYG athletes use the approach style during

competition time. The Zimbabwe National Youth Games athletes need a high level of awareness on stress management.

Hanton *et al.* (2005) found that elite athletes experienced and recalled more demands associated primarily and directly with the sport organization than with competitive performance. Furthermore, this population appeared more likely to experience similar competitive stressors but varied organizational stressors, perhaps because the former are typically common to most athletes' experiences of performance, whereas the latter are generally disparate and subject to numerous socio-cultural, political, economic, occupational, and technological influences. More recently, Fletcher, Hanton and Mellalieu (2012) compared the frequency and content of organizational stressors between elite and non-elite sport performers. They found that the higher skilled participants encountered more stressors than the lower skilled participants.

As a result of tedious schedules, many student-athletes reported having a difficult time incorporating studies into their training schedules (Comeaux & Harrison, 2011; Harris, Altekruze, & Engels, 2003; Cosh & Tully, 2014). Sport and education are seen as a trade-off, one being sacrificed in favour of the other (Cosh & Tully, 2014).

Male and female athletes tend to prioritize academics and athletics differently and consequently experience academic stress differently. Previous studies have shown that females are significantly more likely to report general college stress compared to their male counterparts (Bedewy & Gabriel, 2015; Lin & Huang, 2014), but are superior to their male counterparts in terms of higher scores on high school GPA, SAT scores, college GPA, and graduation rates (Simons & Docherty, 1999; Reynolds, Fisher & Cavil, 2012).

Fletcher and Goodger (2012) investigated the relationship between organizational stressors and burnout in collegiate soccer players. Results revealed multiple organizational stressors linked to athlete burnout comprising training and competition load, training and competition environment, travel arrangements, nutritional issues, risk of injury, leadership style, lack of social support, career and performance development, inadequate communication channels, and role overload. Additional stressors athletes may experience include: extensive time demands placed upon them, injuries, conflict with coaches, pressure to win, and academic demands including tests, assignments, missing classes because of travel and making up assignments (Humphrey, Yow & Bauden, 2000; Wilson & Pritchard, 2005).

For teenagers and young adults in sports, there is the added pressure of the transition between junior and senior level; they start competing at a higher level compared to opponents, and in addition, often also deal with school and moving away from home (Bruner, Munroe-Chandler & Spink, 2008). Due to these demands, transition in an athlete's life can be crucial, and strategies to meet these challenges are therefore important (Pearson & Petitpas, 1990; Samuel & Tenenbaum, 2011).

In another examination of the characteristics of peak performance, Williams and Krane (2001) identified a number of psychological characteristics and mental skills of elite athletes. These included having a high level of motivation and commitment to the task, a well-defined practice and competition routine, and a strong belief in one's ability to perform. Athletes who demonstrate these skills during a performance are presumably in a better position to achieve success than athletes who do not. It intuitively makes sense for the effects of competition on performance to closely resonate with those of observers on performance, given the considerable social comparison and evaluation elements that are present in competition, moreover, a recent meta-analysis yielded only weak support for its predictions when applied to sport performance (Strauss, 2002).

Neil (2011) observes that stressors gave rise to negative appraisals and emotions, but through a further appraisal of their experience, the athletes were able to interpret the thoughts and feelings as facilitative for upcoming performance through an increase in focus and/or effort. Implications of these findings for researchers and practitioners are discussed.

Competition does not always facilitate performance of the set tasks (Strauss, 2002). A more contemporary approach to the investigation of the effects of competition on performance explores potential underlying mechanisms of the competition–performance relationship (Beilock & Gray, 2007). As previously indicated, competition can be considered an acute psychological stress which elicits pressure to perform well. As a consequence, theories designed to explain the effects of emotion/stress/pressure on performance may apply to the competition performance relationship. This section reviewed competition as source of stress and related it to how it affects athletes' performance.

Fear of losing/failure is very simple but a very deadly stressor (Cohn, 2015). Skills and practice time can help athletes gain confidence, which minimizes this kind of stress. However, when athletes are too experienced, they may relax and hence affect their performance (Cohn, 2015).

Most athletes perceive their performance based on wins or losses. External stressors can vary greatly depending on the situation.

Eisenbarth and Petlichkoff (2012) studied the correlation between defined successes and the tendency to perceive an event as threatening. Participants in the study were 200 college athletes who came from three sports classifications: intercollegiate, intermural, and recreational. Two sets of questionnaires were administered as part of the survey. The first questionnaire assessed goal orientations and the second assessed competitive trait anxiety. Competitive trait anxiety was measured through the Sports Anxiety Scale (SAS). The scale measures an individual's disposition to perceive competition as threatening. Overall, the results of the study indicated that goal orientation rather than ego was more significant in predicting anxiety. However, there lacked goal oriented profile to determine competitive trait anxiety.

When individuals are presented with a highly stressful event, their coping responses may either adaptive or maladaptive (Sloan-Power, Boxer, McGuirl & Church, 2012). Given the domains of coping, when athletes lack ability to cope, they resort to avoidance-focused styles that can negatively impact mental health.

These specific stressful situations are common in sport, particularly in areas such as performance expectations (Ayers, Pazmino-Cevallos & Dobos, 2012). When presented with stressful situations, a broad focus is important because of the various activities and responsibilities to which these athletes must commit. Although it only represents one potential stressor among many, Ayers and colleagues (2012) found the importance placed on an athlete's academic eligibility in sport to induce increased levels of stress. Other examples include, having the necessary finances in place, balancing work, family, and social activities (Devonport, Lane, & Biscomb, 2013).

Overwhelming time demand for balancing these commitments has been supported (Ayers et al., 2012), and the pressure to perform athletically often takes priority over academics. Ayers and colleagues (2012) reported that 86% of athletes missed class time due to athletic conflicts, but only 2-3% reported missing athletic contests for other commitments. Unfortunately, the selection of sport participation over academics can have several negative consequences. For example, collegiate athletes often miss many of the benefits available to them in college.

Different reactions to these threats vary by sport and are typically categorized as team (interdependent; e.g., soccer) or individual (independent; e.g., running) (Evans et al., 2012). One

misconception of individual sport is that these athletes do not spend time together or rely on teammates to build important interpersonal relationships (Evans et al., 2012). These athletes interact, and this forms a dynamic that needs to be distinguished from that of team sports. Individual sport can be defined as activities that do not require other individuals to complete a task, and can have specific characteristics such as (1) the use of team scores, (2) training that requires the presence of teammates, and (3) distinct leaders and roles (Evans et al., 2012). Thus, athletes who are independent when performing a specific task still rely on a group in different ways (e.g., training) to perform that task optimally.

2.2 Knowledge Gap

The researcher carried out review of various literatures related to; concept of stress among athletes, athletes' performance in relation to institutional stress and athletes' performance. The critically review showed that there is still need of research to be done on influence of Competition Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance creating a research gap that the current study analyzed influence of Competition Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance in Secondary Schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

2.3 Theoretical Review

The theoretical aspect of this study is informed by Cognitive Activation Theory of stress (CATS) by Lazarus & Folkman (1984). This theoretical perspective defines stress as a relationship between individuals and their environments. First, stress and coping are viewed as manifestations of dynamic and evaluative interplays between individuals and their environments. Secondly, the cognitive theory of stress and coping suggests that stress and coping are bidirectional processes in that individuals are both agents and objects of environmental change. The theory relies on an assumption that individuals engage in a cognitive appraisal of the environmental condition leading to an evaluation of perceived threats. The cognitive processes include coping mechanisms, an attempt to moderate the environment or an internal attempt to regulate the emotional distress caused by the stressor.

The theory further suggests that repeated experiences with a stimulus allow individuals to adapt and regulate themselves (Ursin & Eriksen, 2004). According to the theory experience may

produce discomfort for the individual, arousal and stress is vital to the operation of complex brains. The purpose of arousal is to compel the individual to remove the source of the stress “alarm” and the alarm itself, similar to how it has been argued that the function of effect is to direct action (Frijda, 1996). Or, if not removed, the individual then is able to sustain the activation necessary to handle the stressor. Consequently, the stress experience is part of an adaptive and beneficial system that has survived the test of evolution. CATS theory argues that because the stress alarm occurs when there is a discrepancy between what is desired and what is reality, individuals will associate a probability with the likelihood of abolishing the alarm and its source (Ursin, 2005). This expectancy has a strong influence on the level of arousal. At its simplest, if the person has control and expects a desired outcome, then the alarm may not be activated (i.e., stressors may not be felt, psychologically or physiologically). However, if the future is unpredictable and/or an individual does not have the necessary resources to handle the demands, then the alarm is activated. Further, there are instances when individuals do not possess the necessary resources to handle the situation and dissociating themselves from it thus engaging a passive response that provokes a positive outcome expectation, reducing stress activation.

To account for individual differences in the activation of the stress response, Lazarus (1966) identified six key decisional components within appraisal and the development of stress, three primary components and three secondary components. Primary appraisal of an event involves addressing what is happening and whether the event is worthy of one’s attention (Lazarus, 1993). The individual determines whether the potential stressor is a threat based on previous experiences, knowledge about oneself, and knowledge about the event. Primary appraisal includes three components that are related to the motivational aspects of the encounter with the event. Specifically, primary appraisal includes addressing goal relevance, goal congruence, and the type of ego involvement. Goal relevance indicates whether there is anything at stake to be interfered with by the perceived threat or barrier. If there is nothing to be lost by the presentation of the threat, then no stress response will occur. If the situation is viewed as relevant to the individual’s achievement goals, a stress response will result.

The study will also be informed by Rational-Emotive-Behaviour-Theory (REBT) is one of the cognitive behavioural approaches which was founded in 1955 by an American clinical psychologist, Albert Ellis (Scott, 1995). He was the first to pinpoint that people suffer from stress and other conflicts because they believe things which are false. Ellis maintained that emotional and behavioural disturbance was primarily caused by rigid and absolutistic beliefs in the form of musts, shoulds, have to's, got to's (Melgosa, 2000) - demands we make on ourselves, others, the world. In other words, it is individuals who largely upset themselves rather than events, circumstances or other people. In order to minimize emotional disturbance and produce more goal orientated behaviour, rigid or irrational beliefs are pinpointed, challenged and changed to a rational belief system, according to Ellis, 1972.

The stress management strategies would mainly be devoted to cathartic techniques, relaxation, exercise, healthy eating, positive thinking and 'cooling off periods. These are the suggested strategies towards managing stress in my literature review section. From the REBT perspective, these are essentially short term and palliative methods; unless demandingness is disputed and changed to rational ideas through teaching individuals the ABC model, it is unlikely that stress levels will fall.

When examining the experience of chronic stress for athletes, individual differences become apparent. Stress values mostly fall on the moderate side, yet athletes are significantly more stressed on average than people from the general population; whereas athletes with alarmingly high indicators of stress are mainly elite student athletes (shortly EA) who pursue a school or university career in addition to their elite-level sport (Richartz & Sallen, 2017). Chronic stress seems to play an important role in the dropout of athletic careers (Baron-Thiene & Alfermann, 2015). Exhaustion, depression, and burnout are some of the symptoms often mentioned in connection with chronic stress (Gustafsson, Madigan, & Lundkvist, 2017).

2.4 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Influence of Competition Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance

Figure 1 indicates the relationship between independent, moderating and dependent variables. The independent variable was institutional stress. Affecting this process is the moderating variable was motivation by Games Teachers. These factors can moderate the relationship between independent variables and dependent variable. The model as conceptualized in this study emphasizes on how the independent variables may influence the dependent variables. The study hypothesizes that unmanaged school based stressors is disastrous to athletics by influence their tack performance.

3.0 Research Design

This study undertook an exploratory survey approach with ex-post facto design. *Ex post facto* research, by its very design, investigates the world as it naturally occurs and explores phenomena that have already occurred (Johnson & Christensen, 2008). The study targeted 3,584 form two and three students in schools with high performance in athletics.

Given the sample size of 351 as per Krejcie & Morgan (1970) sampling table, the following formula was used to calculate stratified sample;

$$ss = \frac{z_p}{t_p} Xs$$

Where ss – stratified sample, z_p –zonal population, t_p – target population and s – sample. The sample size distribution for the study is shown in Table 2. The study purposively picked 5 athlete

coaches and 5 Teacher Counselors as key informants to give deeper insight into selected stress factors influencing track performance of Student Athletes. The researcher took half of the sample size to represent both the gender in order to analyze how the different gender responds to stress.

Table 1 Sample Size of Student Athletes in School in Nakuru County

Zone	No. Schools	Total No. of Form		Male Athletes	Female Athletes
		2 and 3 Students	Sample Size		
A	4	430	42	21	21
B	6	620	61	30	30
C	3	664	65	33	32
D	4	820	80	40	40
E	7	1050	103	52	51
Total	24	3584	351	176	175

The study used a structured questionnaire to collect primary data. Descriptive (frequencies and percentages) analysis and inferential statistics such as chi-square test and Pearson’s correlation analyses were used to analyze data after appropriate data coding. Descriptive statistics were used to investigate or explore one variable at a time. To test the hypotheses, chi-square test and Pearson’s correlation analyses were conducted for each hypothesis and the results interpreted leading to the rejection or acceptance of the null hypotheses stated earlier. All hypotheses was tested at $\alpha=.05$.

4.0 Findings and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 :Distribution of Responses on Competition Related Stress

Competition Related Stress	1	2	3	4	5
Unready to wake up in the morning	116(34.1%)	114(33.5%)	90(36.5%)	6(1.8%)	14(4.1%)
Fatigue as I prepare to start the day	106(31.2%)	90(26.5%)	58(17.1%)	28(8.2%)	58(17.1%)
Fear of failure and/or making a mistake	72(21.2%)	64(18.8%)	62(18.2%)	70(20.6%)	72(21.2%)
Athletics competitions not importance	138(40.6%)	38(11.2%)	60(17.6%)	22(6.5%)	82(24.1%)
Feeling of negative evaluated	118(34.7%)	74(21.8%)	80(23.5%)	26(7.6%)	42(12.4%)
Fear of injury inhibit participation	106(31.2%)	76(22.4%)	54(15.9%)	40(11.8%)	64(18.8%)

in athletics						
Time pressures for class work and athletics	94(27.6%)	48(14.1%)	54(15.9%)	44(12.9%)	100(29.4%)	
Expectation has a toll order	122(35.9%)	64(18.8%)	60(17.6%)	52(15.3%)	42(12.4%)	
Forced to participate in school activity	178(52.4%)	42(12.4%)	50(14.7%)	28(8.2%)	42(12.4%)	
Overemphasis affect my performance	112(32.9%)	84(24.7%)	54(15.9%)	46(13.5%)	44(12.9%)	

Data presented in Table 9 indicates that 116(34.1%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I feel unready when I wake up in the morning'* while 114(33.5%) disagreed; 90(36.5%) were undecided; 6(1.8%) agreed and 14(4.1%) completely agreed with the statement. Similarly, 106(31.2%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I feel high levels of fatigue as I prepare to start my day in school'* while 90(26.5%) disagreed; 58(17.1%) were undecided; 28(8.2%) agreed and 58(17.1%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 72(21.2%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I have constant fear of failure and/or making a mistake as I related with teachers and fellow students'* while 64(18.8%) disagreed; 62(18.2%) were undecided; 70(20.6%) agreed and 72(21.2%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: *'I no longer see athletics competitions to be of importance to me and my school as I used to feel'* it was observed that 138(40.6%) completely disagreed; 38(11.2%) disagreed; 60(17.6%) were undecided; 22(6.5%) agreed and 82(24.1%) completely agreed. Similarly, 118(34.7%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I fear that I will be negative evaluation whenever I attempt anything in school'* while 74(21.8%) disagreed; 80(23.5%) were undecided; 26(7.6%) agreed and 42(12.4%) completely agreed with the statement.

It was also observed that 106(31.2%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I have this feeling of fear of injury which prevent me from participating in athletics'* while 76(22.4%) disagreed; 54(15.9%) were undecided; 40(11.8%) agreed and 64(18.8%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: *'I have time pressures to do my class work and participate in athletics'* it was observed that 94(27.6%) completely disagreed; 48(14.1%) disagreed; 54(15.9%) were undecided; 44(12.9%) agreed and 100(29.4%) completely agreed. It was also observed that 122(35.9%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'My feeling of expectation from self and others has taken a toll order on me'* while

64(18.8%) disagreed; 60(17.6%) were undecided; 52(15.3%) agreed and 42(12.4%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: '*I feel my teachers force me to participate in the activity at in school*' it was observed that 178(52.4%) completely disagreed; 42(12.4%) disagreed; 50(14.7%) were undecided; 28(8.2%) agreed and 42(12.4%) completely agreed. Similarly, 112(32.9%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*The school overemphasis on outcome scares me and affect my performance*' while 84(24.7%) disagreed; 54(15.9%) were undecided; 46(13.5%) agreed and 44(12.9%) completely agreed with the statement.

The levels of completion related stress was conceptualized as a composite variable derived from the averages of non-missing responses on 10 items. The overall averages were divided into 3 categories: Low; Moderate and High. The expected highest score per respondent was 50, and therefore, transition points were $x \leq 17$ for Low; $x \geq 17 \leq 34$ for Moderate and $x \geq 34$ for high levels of completion related stress.

Table 2: Distribution of Responses on Athletes Track Performance

Institutional Stress	1	2	3	4	5
I worry quite a bit about what the teachers think of my performance.	40(11.8%)	112(32.9%)	38(11.2%)	36(10.6%)	114(33.5%)
I tend to do lots of planning about how to reach my goals.	48(14.1%)	76(22.4%)	36(10.6%)	26(7.6%)	154(45.3%)
I feel confident that I will play well.	34(10%)	80(23.5%)	70(20.6%)	38(11.2%)	118(34.7%)
When a coach or manager criticizes me, I become upset rather than feel helped.	78(22.9%)	98(28.8%)	60(17.6%)	46(13.5%)	58(17.1%)
It is easy for me to keep distracting thoughts from interfering with something I am watching or listening to.	68(20%)	82(24.1%)	66(19.4%)	64(18.8%)	60(17.6%)
I put a lot of pressure on myself by worrying about how I will perform.	56(16.5%)	96(28.2%)	36(10.6%)	44(12.9%)	108(31.8%)
I set my own performance goals for each practice.	22(6.5%)	74(21.8%)	64(18.8%)	58(17.1%)	122(35.9%)
I don't have to be pushed to practice or play hard; I give 100%.	50(14.7%)	90(26.5%)	38(11.2%)	44(12.9%)	118(34.7%)
If a coach criticizes or yells at me, I correct the mistake without getting upset	56(16.5%)	72(21.2%)	54(15.9%)	46(13.5%)	112(32.9%)

about it.					
I handle unexpected situations in my sport very well.	56(16.5%)	90(26.5%)	56(16.5%)	56(16.5%)	82(24.1%)
When things are going badly, I tell myself to keep calm, and this works for me.	58(17.1%)	80(23.5%)	56(16.5%)	48(14.1%)	98(28.8%)
The more pressure there is during a game, the more I enjoy it.	52(15.3%)	98(28.8%)	48(14.1%)	46(13.5%)	96(28.2%)
While competing, I worry about making mistakes or failing to come through.	82(24.1%)	74(21.8%)	54(15.9%)	60(17.6%)	70(20.6%)
I have my own game plan worked out in my head long before the game begins.	72(21.2%)	80(23.5%)	60(17.6%)	40(11.8%)	88(25.9%)
When I feel myself getting too tense, I can quickly relax my body and calm myself.	60(17.6%)	78(22.9%)	56(16.5%)	54(15.9%)	92(27.1%)
To me, pressure situations are challenges that I welcome.	80(23.5%)	94(27.6%)	46(13.5%)	42(12.4%)	78(22.9%)
I think about and imagine what will happen if I fail.	62(18.2%)	82(24.1%)	64(18.8%)	40(11.8%)	92(27.1%)
I maintain emotional control regardless of how things are going for me.	52(15.3%)	66(19.4%)	46(13.5%)	60(17.6%)	116(34.1%)
It is easy for me to direct my attention and focus on a single object or person.	52(15.3%)	72(21.2%)	46(13.5%)	64(18.8%)	106(31.2%)
When I fail to reach my goals, it makes me try even harder.	50(14.7%)	60(17.6%)	44(12.9%)	52(15.3%)	134(39.4%)
I improve my skills by listening carefully to advice and instruction from coaches and managers.	42(12.4%)	56(16.5%)	38(11.2%)	60(17.6%)	144(42.4%)
I make fewer mistakes when the pressure is on because I concentrate better.	54(15.9%)	88(25.9%)	38(11.2%)	66(19.4%)	94(27.6%)

Data presented in Table 2 indicates that 40(11.8%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I worry quite a bit about what the teachers think of my performance'* while 112(32.9%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 36(10.6%) agreed and 114(33.5%) completely agreed with the statement. Similarly, 48(14.1%) of respondents completely disagreed

with the statement *'I tend to do lots of planning about how to reach my goals'* while 76(22.4%) disagreed; 36(10.6%) were undecided; 26(7.6%) agreed and 154(45.3%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 34(10%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I feel confident that I will play well'* while 80(23.5%) disagreed; 70(20.6%) were undecided; 38(11.2%) agreed and 118(34.7%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: *'When a coach or manager criticizes me, I become upset rather than feel helped'* it was observed that 78(22.9%) completely disagreed; 98(28.8%) disagreed; 60(17.6%) were undecided; 46(13.5%) agreed and 58(17.1%) completely agreed. Similarly, 68(20%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'It is easy for me to keep distracting thoughts from interfering with something I am watching or listening to'* while 82(24.1%) disagreed; 66(19.4%) were undecided; 64(18.8%) agreed and 60(17.6%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 56(16.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I put a lot of pressure on myself by worrying about how I will perform'* while 96(28.2%) disagreed; 36(10.6%) were undecided; 44(12.9%) agreed and 108(31.8%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: *'I set my own performance goals for each practice'* it was observed that 22(6.5%) completely disagreed; 74(21.8%) disagreed; 64(18.8%) were undecided; 58(17.1%) agreed and 122(35.9%) completely agreed. It was observed that 50(14.7%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I don't have to be pushed to practice or play hard; I give 100%'* while 90(26.5%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 44(12.9%) agreed and 118(34.7%) completely agreed with the statement. Similarly, 56(16.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'If a coach criticizes or yells at me, I correct the mistake without getting upset about it'* while 72(21.2%) disagreed; 54(15.9%) were undecided; 46(13.5%) agreed and 112(32.9%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 56(16.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I handle unexpected situations in my sport very well'* while 90(26.5%) disagreed; 56(16.5%) were undecided; 56(16.5%) agreed and 82(24.1%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: *'When things are going badly, I tell myself to keep calm, and this works for me'* it was observed that 58(17.1%) completely disagreed; 80(23.5%) disagreed; 56(16.5%) were undecided; 48(14.1%) agreed and 98(28.8%) completely agreed. Similarly, 52(15.3%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'The more pressure there is during a game, the more I enjoy it'* while 98(28.8%) disagreed; 48(14.1%) were

undecided; 46(13.5%) agreed and 96(28.2%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 82(24.1%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*While competing, I worry about making mistakes or failing to come through*' while 74(21.8%) disagreed; 54(15.9%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 70(20.6%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: '*I have my own game plan worked out in my head long before the game begins*' it was observed that 72(21.2%) completely disagreed; 80(23.5%) disagreed; 60(17.6%) were undecided; 40(11.8%) agreed and 88(25.9%) completely agreed. Similarly, 60(17.6%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*When I feel myself getting too tense, I can quickly relax my body and calm myself*' while 78(22.9%) disagreed; 56(16.5%) were undecided; 54(15.9%) agreed and 92(27.1%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 80(23.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*To me, pressure situations are challenges that I welcome*' while 94(27.6%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 42(12.4%) agreed and 78(22.9%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: '*I think about and imagine what will happen if I fail*' it was observed that 62(18.2%) completely disagreed; 82(24.1%) disagreed; 64(18.8%) were undecided; 40(11.8%) agreed and 92(27.1%) completely agreed. It was observed that 52(15.3%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I maintain emotional control regardless of how things are going for me*' while 66(19.4%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 116(34.1%) completely agreed with the statement.

Similarly, 52(15.3%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*It is easy for me to direct my attention and focus on a single object or person*' while 72(21.2%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 64(18.8%) agreed and 106(31.2%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 50(14.7%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*When I fail to reach my goals, it makes me try even harder*' while 60(17.6%) disagreed; 44(12.9%) were undecided; 52(15.3%) agreed and 134(39.4%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: '*I improve my skills by listening carefully to advice and instruction from coaches and managers*' it was observed that 42(12.4%) completely disagreed; 56(16.5%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 144(42.4%) completely agreed. Similarly, 54(15.9%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I make fewer mistakes when the pressure is on because I concentrate better*' while 88(25.9%)

disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 66(19.4%) agreed and 94(27.6%) completely agreed with the statement.

The level of institutional related stress was conceptualized as a composite variable derived from the averages of non-missing responses on 22 items. The overall averages were divided into 3 categories: Low; Moderate and High. The expected highest score per respondent was 50, and therefore, transition points were $x \leq 37$ for Low; $x \geq 38 \leq 74$ for Moderate and $x \geq 75$ for high levels of completion related stress. The findings of the study are presented on Table 2

4.2 Inferential Statistics on the Relationship between Competition Related Stress and Athletes' Track Performance

Table 3: Simple Regression Analysis of the influence of competition related stress on student athletes' track performance

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	431.596	1	431.596	17.502	.000 ^b
Residual	8334.815	338	24.659		
Total	8766.412	339			

From the Table 23 it can be seen that the F-Value significant ($F(1,338)=17.502$, $p=0.000$) implying that completion related stress has significant influence on student athletes' track performance. Competition stress related factors were capable of predicting student athletes' track performance in secondary schools. The null hypothesis (H_{01}): that there is no statistically significant influence of competition related stress on student track athletes' performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that competition related stress is a reliable predictor of student athletes' track performance in secondary schools.

Table 24 present the regression coefficients of the influence of competition related stress on student athletes' track performance.

Table 4: Regression Coefficients of the influence of Competition Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1 (Constant)	16.685	1.374		12.141	.000
Competition Stress	2.827	.676	.222	4.184	.000

The results indicated that the beta value was significant ($\beta=.332$, $p=0.000$). The simple regression model that can be used to predict student athletes' track performance from competition related stress is given by

$$Y = 16.685 + 2.827X_1 + \varepsilon \text{ where;}$$

Y = Students athletes track performance and

X_1 = competition related stress

Based on the results from the study, competition related stress can influence students athletes track performance. This finding is supported by Bruner, Munroe-Chandler and Spink (2008) who found out those teenagers and young adults in sports face added pressure of the transition between junior and senior level; they start competing at a higher level with greater opponents, and often also deal with school and moving away from home. Due to these demands this transition and period in an athlete's life can be crucial, and strategies to meet these challenges are therefore important (Pearson & Petitpas, 1990; Samuel & Tenenbaum, 2011).

Further, the results on influence of completion related stress on student athletes performance is supported by a study conducted by Fletcher, Hanton and Mellalieu (2012) who compared the frequency and content of organizational stressors between elite and non-elite sport performers. They found that the higher skilled participants encountered more stressors than the lower skilled participants. A comparative influence of competition related stress between male and female athletes was found that females are significantly more likely to report general college stress compared to their male counterparts (Bedewy & Gabriel, 2015; Lin & Huang, 2014).

The results is further supported by the fact that when athletes are too results oriented, it takes away from the way that they should perform (Cohn, 2015). This is because most athletes perceive their performance based on wins or losses. Being focused on the present is good but only if it does not take away potential to improve in the future. External stressors can vary greatly depending on the situation. Finding of competition related stress as a predictor of student

athletes' track performance is further supported by the fact that athletes enable them to accomplish tasks through; (1) the use of team scores, (2) training that requires the presence of teammates, and (3) distinct leaders and roles (Evans et al., 2012). Thus, athletes who are independent when performing a specific task still rely on a group in different ways (e.g., training) to perform that task optimally.

Lastly, the finding is supported by Neil (2011) who observes that stressors gave rise to negative appraisals and emotions, but through a further appraisal of their experience, the athletes were able to interpret the thoughts and feelings as facilitative for upcoming performance through an increase in focus and/or effort. Implications of these findings for researchers and practitioners are discussed.

5.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

5.3. Conclusions

The study examined influence of competition related stress influences students' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study established that competition related stress negatively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

Ho₁: There is no statistically significant influence of competition related stress on student track athletes' performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

The hypothesis was tested using simple regression analysis. The simple regression analysis showed that;

1. There was a positive relationship between competition related stress and student athletes' track performance in secondary schools ($r = .222$).
2. Competition related stress accounted for 4.9% ($r^2 = 0.49$) variation in relation to student athletes track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County.
3. Competition related stress had significant statistical influence ($(F(1,338) = 17.502, p = .000)$) students' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Strategies for boosting positive competition related stress should be put in place in secondary schools as a means to boosting track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.
2. The professionals involved in management of sports and games as well as guidance and counselling departments should come up with adequate programmes and ways of managing institutional related stress to mitigate against the negative influences it has on track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

References

- Ayers, K., Pazmino-Cevallos, M., & Doboise, C. (2012). The 20-hour rule: Student athletes time commitment to athletics and academics. *Virginia Journal*, 33(1), 22- 26.
- Baron-Thiene, A., & Alfermann, D. (2015). Personal characteristics as predictors for dual career dropout versus continuation. A prospective study of adolescent athletes from German elite sport schools. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 21, 42–49.
- Bedewy, D., & Gabriel, A. (2015). Examining perceptions of academic stress and its sources among university students: The Perception of Academic Stress Scale. *Health Psychology Open*, 2(2), 2055102915596714.
- Cohn, P. (2015). *Why Fear of Failure Leads to Tentative Play*. Peak Performance Sports. Retrieved from http://www.peaksports.com/sports_psychology_blog/?p=851
- Comeaux, E., & Harrison, C. K. (2011). A conceptual model of academic success for student–athletes. *Educational Researcher*, 40(5), 235-245.
- Cosh, S., & Tully, P. J. (2014). “All I have to do is pass”: A discursive analysis of student athletes' talk about prioritising sport to the detriment of education to overcome stressors encountered in combining elite sport and tertiary education. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 15(2), 180-189.
- Cooke, Andrew Michael (2010). *Effects of competition on performance, and the underlying psychophysiological mechanisms* (unpublished PhD. Thesis), University of Birmingham, England.
- Devonport, T. J., Lane, A. M., & Biscomb, K. (2013). Exploring coping strategies used by national adolescent netball players across domains. *Journal of Clinical Sport Psychology*, 7, 161-177.

- Eisenbarth, C. A., & Petlichkoff, L. M. (2012). Independent and Interactive Effects of Task and Ego Orientations in Predicting Competitive Trait Anxiety among College-Age Athletes. *Journal of Sport Behavior*, 35(4), 387-405.
- Evans, B. M., Eys, M. A., & Bruner, M. W. (2012). Seeing the “we” in “me” sports: The need to consider individual sport team environments. *Canadian Psychology*, 53, 301-308.
- Fletcher, D., Hanton, S., & Mellalieu, S. D. (2006). An organizational stress-review: Conceptual and theoretical issues in competitive sport. In S. Hanton & S. D. Mellalieu (Eds.), *Literature review in sport psychology* (pp. 321–374). Hauppauge, NY: Nova Science
- Gustafsson, H., Madigan, D. J., & Lundkvist, E. (2017). Burnout in athletes. In R. Fuchs & M. Gerber (Eds.), *Stress regulation und Sport* [Stress regulation and sports]. Heidelberg: Springer.
- Hamilton, R., Scott, D., & Macdougall, M., (2007). Assessing the effectiveness of Self-Talk interventions on endurance performance. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 19(3): 226-239.
- Hanton, S. & Connaughton, D. (2002). Perceived control of anxiety and its relationship with self-confidence performance: A qualitative explanation. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 73, 87-97.
- Hanton, S., Fletcher, D., & Coughlan, G. (2005). Stress in elite sport performers: A comparative study of competitive and organizational stressors. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 23, 1129-1141.
- Humprey, J. H., Yow, D.A. & Bauden, W.W. (2000). *Stress in college athletes: Causes, consequences and coping*. Binghamton NY: The Haworth Half-Court press.
- Jayanthat, K. and Ubayachandra, E.G. (2015). Going for gold medals: Factors affecting olympic performance. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 5, (6).
- Lazarus, R. S. (1966). *Psychological stress and the coping process*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Lazarus, R. S. (1983). *Puzzles in the study of daily hassle*. Paper presented at conference entitled integrative perspectives in youths Development; Person and Ecology. Berlin, West Germany.
- Lin, S. H., & Huang, Y. C. (2014). Life stress and academic burnout. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 15(1), 77-90.
- Lombardo, E. R. Tan, G. Jensen, M. P. & Anderson, K. O. (2005). Anger management style and association with self-efficacy and pain in male veterans. *The Journal of Pain*, 6, 765-770. doi:10.1016/j.jpain.2005.07.003
- Melgosa, Julian. (2000). *Less Stress*. Editorial Safeliz: Madrid.

- Mellalieu, S. D., Hanton, S., & Fletcher, D. (2006). A competitive anxiety review: Recent directions in sport psychology research. In S. Hanton, & S. D. Mellalieu (Eds.), *Literature reviews in sport psychology* (pp. 1-45). Hauppauge, NY: Nova Science.
- Neila, Rich; Sheldon, Hantona; Stephen, D. Mellalieub; David, Fletcher (2011). Competition stress and emotions in sport performers: The role of further appraisals. [*Psychology of Sport and Exercise* 12 \(4\)](#) 460-470
- Ongonga, J. O., Okwara, M. O. and Okello, T. M. (2010). Sports and Secondary Education in Kenya. *International Research Journals*, 1 (11), 607-617.
- Pearson, R.E. and Petitpas, A.J. (2000). Transitions of Athletes: Developmental and Preventive Perspectives, *Journal of Counseling and Development*, 69(1).
- Richartz, A., & Sallen, J. (2017). *Combining elite sports and academic career. Chronic stressors, protective resources and preventative approaches. Multiple stressors in the contexts of health and society* (pp. 65–83). Berlin: LIT.
- Samuel, R.D. & Tenenbaum, G. (1011). The Role of Change in Athletes' Careers: A Scheme of Change for Sport Psychology Practice, *The Sports Psychologist*, 5(2)
- Sloan-Power, E. M., Boxer, P., McGuirl, C., & Church, R. (2012). Coping zone construction and mapping: An exploratory study of contextual coping, PTSD, and childhood violence exposure in urban areas. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 28, 1741- 1764.
- Stough, C., Clements, M., Wallish, L., & Downey, D. (2009). *Emotional intelligence in sport: theoretical linkages and preliminary empirical relationships from basketball*. Springer US Press.
- Ursin, H. (2005). Press stop to start: The role of inhibition for choice and health. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 30: 1059-1065.
- Ursin, H., & Eriksen, H. R. (2004). The Cognitive Activation Theory of Stress. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 29, 567-592.
- Wilson, G. S., Pritchard, M. E., & Schaffer, J. (2004). Athletic status and drinking behavior in college students: the influence of gender and coping styles. *Journal of American College Health*, 52, 269-273.